

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF SEMI-CRYSTALLINE,
THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR
ELEVATED TEMPERATURE SERVICE

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties of a high temperature semi-crystalline polymer, HTX, and continuous fibre composites using HTX as the matrix are discussed in the context of the glass-rubber temperature transition (T_g). Values of T_g obtained using dynamic mechanical tests at high frequencies have been shifted to lower frequencies typical of engineering loading, using the activation energy. This enables plots of modulus vs temperature to be obtained for polymer and composite at typical times under load. When this is done the T_g of HTX is still greater than 200°C. This has been confirmed by independent measurements on the composite of compressive strength and creep at a range of temperatures up to 220°C. The composite retains a high proportion of compressive strength at temperatures up to 180°C and shows negligible creep in the range (23-180)°C.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre reinforced composites with thermoplastic matrices are gaining growing acceptance as structural materials for aircraft (1). Semi-crystalline polymers have a number of attractive features as composite matrices and Aromatic Polymer Composites (APC) based on poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK) have been shown to combine high toughness, environmental resistance and the opportunity to utilise a range of

fabrication techniques. The long-term service temperature of the PEEK/carbon fibre composites is believed to be in the region of 120°C (2) which represents a limitation in some applications. More recently a higher temperature thermoplastic polymer, HTX, has been developed and properties of the polymer and composite have been described (3). The basic properties of continuous carbon fibre reinforced HTX, APC (HTX), are given in Table 1.

The glass-rubber transition temperature (T_g) is a particularly important feature because of its frequent use as a guide to maximum service temperature. One method commonly used for measuring T_g is Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), where a specimen can be vibrated at a constant controlled frequency, at a resonant frequency or to a constant deformation. The frequencies of vibration are typically in the range (1-30) Hz and as such the measurements are made at small elapsed times under load which are not representative of typical engineering applications. Hence it is necessary to correlate such testing with mechanical evaluations at a range of temperatures and times under load.

Consequently the aim of this paper is to clarify some of these issues and in particular to examine the property-temperature relations for HTX and APC(HTX) in such a way that is relevant to its use as an engineering composite.

TABLE 1

BASIC MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL APC(HTX) COMPOSITE

(From Ref (1))

Reinforced with 61% by volume of Continuous Carbon Fibre.

Longitudinal Tensile Modulus	132 GPa
Longitudinal Tensile Strength	1984 MPa
Longitudinal Compressive Strength	1136 MPa
Longitudinal Flexural Strength	1775 MPa
Transverse Flexural Strength	90 MPa
Short-Beam Shear Strength	95 MPa

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Evaluations of HTX polymer were carried out on specimens taken from 3mm thick, compression moulded panels. Evaluations of the composite were on specimens taken from compression moulded panels of carbon fibre/HTX pre-preg tape. The moulding conditions have been described previously (3) and the panels varied from 4-ply (0.5mm) to 40-ply (5.0mm) in thickness.

DMA Testing

Dynamic mechanical properties were obtained on samples of polymer and composite. DMA testing on the polymer was conducted with a Polymer Laboratories Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analyser at a range of fixed frequencies from 0.1Hz to 10Hz. DMA was performed on unidirectionally reinforced composite at 0° and 90° relative to reinforcing fibres using a DuPont 981 Mechanical Analyser (resonance frequency method).

Polymer Mechanical Testing

Various tests were performed to characterise the mechanical properties of the polymer. These properties included modulus, compressive yield stress and two fracture mechanics parameters. Uniaxial compression tests were performed in order to obtain a compressive yield stress using an adaption of a method described in an ISO document (4). The fracture toughness measurements were conducted on single edged notched three-point bend specimens at a test speed of 1m/s and a temperature of -65°C. It was verified that the fracture mechanics results were plane strain, geometry independent values by the analysis summarised by Hashemi and Williams (5).

Composite Mechanical Testing

Compressive strength was measured at a variety of temperatures on unidirectional carbon fibre/HTX. The test method used was adapted from the ASTM D-695 Test Method, in which 40-ply composite panels were

prepared and the centre section machined down to provide a central gauge length 6mm long and 1mm thick.

Creep properties were measured at a variety of temperatures on 16-ply quasi-isotropic composite panels. Creep tests were conducted in tension on parallel sided specimens using a servohydraulic Instron 8033 where strain was measured with an extensometer clipped to the specimen.

Crystallinity Measurements

Crystallinity was measured on polymer and composite specimens from the heat of fusion in a DSC test using Perkin Elmer DSC-4 and DSC-7 machines.

RESULTS

HTX Polymer

The crystallinity of the HTX polymer mouldings was 17%. The mechanical properties of the HTX polymer are given in Table 2. These confirm that HTX has relatively high modulus and yield stress, however, this has been achieved without compromising toughness. The basic mechanical properties lie within the ranges that have been recommended as targets for composite matrices (6).

TABLE 2
MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HTX POLYMER

Crystallinity 17%

Tensile Modulus (Measured 20 secs, 23°C, 0.2% Strain)	3.1 GN/m ²
Compressive Yield Strength (23°C)	131 MN/m ²
Fracture Toughness Properties	
K _{IC} (-65°C)	1.4 MN/m ^{3/2}
G _{IC} (-65°C)	1.0 kJ/m ²

Figure 1. $\text{Tan } \delta$ vs temperature for HTX polymer at various frequencies.

The plots of $\text{tan } \delta$ vs temperature from the DMA tests are shown in Fig 1 for three frequencies. At the lowest frequency of 0.1Hz the measured Tg was 209°C and Figure 1 shows that the observed Tg increases with frequency. The relationship between the observed temperature of the transition and DMA test frequency is described by an Arrhenius type equation(7):

$$f = f_0 \exp(-\Delta H/RT) \quad \text{————— (1)}$$

where f is the test frequency
 f_0 is a constant
 ΔH is the activation energy
 R is the Gas constant and
 T is the test temperature

Using the results in Figure 1 the activation energy was calculated as 224 kcal/mole.

The Tg at various times under load can be calculated using the activation energy. For example at a time under load of 20 seconds (which is typical for the definition of an engineering modulus) the Tg is 203°C.

There are further complications in simply using a modulus measured from the DMA technique. The modulus is derived from a stiffness which itself cannot be precisely measured; in addition geometric considerations in the test lead to a need for several corrections to the measured

stiffness prior to calculation of a modulus. In order to obviate these difficulties, the DMA modulus axis can be replaced by a modulus scale which is calibrated by a single value derived from an accurate modulus obtained at 23°C in a slow rate test. The time under load is selected to be commensurate with the time used in shifting the temperature scale.

Using this approach a temperature shifted and calibrated modulus-temperature function can be obtained, and such a plot is shown for HTX polymer in Figure 2. It can be seen from this plot that polymer maintains its stiffness at temperatures in excess of 180°C, even when all corrections have been included to ensure the data reflect the response to strain rates likely to be encountered in practical applications.

Figure 2. Tensile modulus vs temperature for HTX polymer. Reference modulus defined at 20 sec, 0.2% strain.

Carbon Fibre/HTX Composite

The experimental DMA data on the composite were converted to engineering modulus vs temperature data using calibration values from a three-point bending test and using the activation energy of 224 kcal/mole to shift the temperature axis. For the composite this may result in an overshift because there is only 39% by volume of HTX polymer in the composite, and hence the calculated modulus-temperature data are probably conservative. The resulting engineering modulus-temperature plots are

illustrated in Figures 3 and 4 for the 0° and 90° directions respectively. There is little loss in stiffness up to 180°C and as would be expected the 0° orientation shows greater retention of modulus above T_g . However it can be seen that for both orientations some stiffness is retained above T_g due to the semi-crystalline nature of the polymer, the level of crystallinity in these specimens being 17%.

Figure 3. Longitudinal modulus vs temperature for unidirectional carbon fibre/HTX.
Reference modulus defined at 60 sec, 0.2% strain.

Figure 4. Transverse modulus vs temperature for unidirectional carbon fibre/HTX.
Reference modulus defined at 60sec, 0.2% strain.

Compressive strength was examined in the temperature range -55°C to $+220^{\circ}\text{C}$. The crystallinity of the panel from which the in the compression specimens were taken was also 17%. At temperatures below 23°C a delamination failure sometimes occurred between the machined gauge section and the bulk of the specimen. This did not appear to strongly influence the magnitude of the compressive strength, at least within the typical scatter bands of $\pm (5 - 10)\%$. The measured compressive strength is plotted as a function of temperature in Figure 5. The compressive strength remains high at temperatures up to the T_g of the polymer, and exceeds 1000MN/m^2 for temperatures up to 180°C . At temperatures above 180°C the modulus of the matrix reduces as shown in Figure 4, due to the glass-rubber transition and therefore the resistance to compressive buckling is considerably reduced leading to a fall in compressive strength.

Figure 5. Longitudinal compressive strength vs temperature for unidirectional carbon fibre/HTX.

Tensile creep tests were conducted on carbon fibre/HTX at temperatures of 23°C , 120°C , 150°C and 180°C . The creep curves are shown in Figure 6. The constant applied stresses were chosen to give a short-term axial strain of 0.5%. The combination of a short-time stress-strain curve with the experimental creep curve enables a computerised interpolation to provide families of creep curves at a range of stresses and cross-plots of stress-time and hence modulus-time plots to be

Figure 6. Tensile creep at various temperatures for carbon fibre/HTX Lay-Up $(-45/0/+45/90)_2s$. Applied Stress 250 MN/m^2 .

obtained (8). Such information provides the necessary engineering design data at relevant times and temperatures. The creep results confirm that quasi-isotropic carbon fibre/HTX shows negligible creep in the temperature range 23–180°C over the times examined of up to 10^5 seconds (~ 1 day). By the same token it would be expected to show negligible relaxation under similar conditions.

DISCUSSION

The results confirm that HTX polymer retains a high proportion of its room temperature modulus at temperatures up to 180°C. Even when shifted to a 20-second measurement typical of engineering applications, the T_g is 203°C. This high T_g is reflected in the high retention of composite properties at elevated temperatures. For example 85% of the room temperature transverse modulus is retained at 180°C even when shifted to a time under load of 60 seconds. Even greater retention is seen for the longitudinal modulus with virtually no change in the range 23–180°C. The matrix modulus is also the controlling factor in determining compressive strength and independent compressive tests show a 78% retention of compressive strength at 180°C compared to room temperature. The creep tests on quasi-isotropic laminates also confirm negligible creep over the temperature range 23°C – 180°C. All these results show that HTX polymer and HTX matrix composites possess the engineering properties required for structural applications at temperatures up to 180°C. Above 180°C the properties start to fall due

to the glass-rubber transition of the polymer, however useful properties are still retained due to the semi-crystalline nature of the polymer. The exact amount of retention will depend upon the level of crystallinity, the particular property examined and the time under load.

CONCLUSIONS

The simple use of DMA results can give a misleading picture of temperature performance and it is necessary to have a full understanding of the effect of frequency or time under load on the observed processes. This can be achieved by measuring the activation energy for the polymer and shifting the Tg process to the relevant rate or frequency. When this is done for HTX polymer and carbon fibre/HTX composite the Tg process occurs at a temperature greater than 200°C even when shifted to times under load that are typical of service applications. A good correlation is seen between independent measurements of polymer modulus vs temperature, composite modulus vs temperature (both 0° and 90°) and composite compressive strength vs temperature. These results combined with the creep results confirm that HTX polymer and composites retain engineering properties at temperatures up to 180°C.

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